

Membrane potential based assay for SLC2A9 using HEK-293 SLC2A9 OE cells

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Assay description

FLIPR® membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC2A9. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1). SLC2A9 is a facilitative urate transporter located in the apical and basolateral membrane of the proximal convoluted tubule of the kidney. Two isoforms, a long one (isoform 1) and a short one (isoform 2) have been described showing divergences at the N-terminal. The transport mediated by SLC2A9 is electrogenic and therefore eligible to be studied using FLIPR® membrane potential assay.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR® membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

To develop a functional recombinant SLC2A9 cell-based assay, HEK-293 cells were stably transfected with the SLC2A9 isoform 1 and isoform 2 coding sequences. Mock controls (transfected with the empty plasmids) were generated in parallel. Two rounds of limiting dilution led to the isolation of pure clones, the final clones (one for each isoform) were subjected to pharmacological characterization and tested to verify that the assay fulfils HTS quality criteria in terms of robustness and reproducibility.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 20'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂.

Membrane Potential assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 30 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of FMP-Blue-Dye (0.5X dye dissolved in Standard Tyrode's Buffer as indicated in the manufacturer manual) and plates analysed at Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX reader using a λ_{exc} 531nm/λ_{em} 593 nm filter (or at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λ_{exc} 510 - 545nm / λ_{em} 565 - 625 nm filter).

To test pharmacology 10 µL/well of Orotic acid D/R (3X in Standard Tyrode's Buffer; 0.2% DMSO final concentration), starting from 10 mM, 1:2 dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) was online injected at the plate reader. Uric acid was also tested as SLC2A9 substrate, in D/R, starting from 1.25 mM, 1:2 dilution steps.

To assess robustness, reproducibility and amenability to high-throughput screening at least three 384-well plates were run consecutively, using the following plate layouts for one (Figure 2) or double injection protocol (Figure 3) respectively.

Figure 2. Compound plate layout for single injection protocol.

Figure 3. Compound plate layout for double injection protocol. First injection plate on the left and second injection plate on the right.

Data analysis

Hamamatsu FDSS7000EX measurements were analysed by using the Hamamatsu software (FDSS7000EX/ μ CELL software U8524-03A). Absolute Response (Relative Fluorescence unit, RFU) was obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection). Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC).

Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC_{50}/IC_{50} values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 8).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC2A9
Synonyms	Glucose Transporter Type 9, GLUT9
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 2 ((Facilitated Glucose Transporter))
UniProt ID	Q9NRM0
RESOLUTE Cell ID	HEK-293/SLC2A9 isoform 1 K5 p4 and HEK-293/SLC2A9 isoform 2 K2 p4 (Axxam cell lines)

Assay data

<p>ISOFORM1</p>	Compound name (1)	Orotic acid
	PubChem CID	967
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Fisher Scientific, #AAA1859418
	Mode of action	Substrate
<p>ISOFORM2</p>	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 1 mM for both isoforms
	Compound name (2)	Uric acid
	PubChem CID	1175
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Santa Cruz Biotechnology, #sc-213135
Mode of action	Substrate	
Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 0.3 mM for isoform 1, not calculable for isoform 2	

<p>ISOFORM1</p> <p>ISOFORM2</p>	<p>Z' factor calculated as</p> $RZ' = 1 - \frac{3 \cdot RSD(CR_p) + 3 \cdot RSD(SR_p)}{ \langle CR_p \rangle - \langle SR_p \rangle }$ <p>in single (left panel) and double (right panel) injection protocol</p>
<p>ISOFORM1</p> <p>ISOFORM2</p>	<p>Intraplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{CR} = \frac{SD(CR_p)}{ \overline{SR_p} - \overline{CR_p} } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Intraplate}_{SR} = \frac{SD(SR_p)}{ \overline{SR_p} - \overline{CR_p} } \times 100$ <p>in single (left panel) and double (right panel) injection protocol</p>
<p>ISOFORM1</p> <p>ISOFORM2</p>	<p>Interplate Variability calculated as</p> $\text{Variability Interplate}_{CR} = \frac{\overline{CR_p} - \text{mean}(\overline{CR_{p,d}})}{ \overline{CR_{p,d}} - \overline{SR_{p,d}} } \times 100$ $\text{Variability Interplate}_{SR} = \frac{\overline{SR_p} - \text{mean}(\overline{SR_{p,d}})}{ \overline{CR_{p,d}} - \overline{SR_{p,d}} } \times 100$ <p>in single (left panel) and double (right panel) injection protocol</p>

Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC2A9 showed a dose-dependent cell hyperpolarization indicating that Orotic acid is transported inside the cells.

The assay fulfils the HTS quality criteria in terms of RZ' and intraplate and interplate variability in both single and double injection protocols.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).